

A CLINICO – PHARMACEUTICAL STUDY ON BHRINGRAJ TAILA W.S.R TO KHALITYA (BAHYA CHIKITSA) - A SINGLE CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Now a days most of the people are suffering from hair fall irrespective of their age factor. Generally many people are suffering from this disease whether they are young or old. In Ayurveda loss of hair is correlated with “**khalitya roga**”. It is primarily a **pitta** predominant **tridoshajanya vyadhi**. In present era hairfall takes place due to some factors like sedentary life style, unhealthy diets, systemic and sleep disturbances, overusing of hair products, hormone imbalance etc. Acharya Sushruta and Acharya vagbhatta involved khalitya in kshudra roga and shiroroga respectively. A patient of khalitya roga visit in Guru Nanak ayurvedic college and hospital, sri muktsar sahib. The probable complaints were hair fall, dryness of hair and premature greying. As per the case, Patient was suggested to use bhringraj taila for hair as external application, which was prepared in the pharmacy of Guru Nanak Ayurvedic college and hospital, Sri Muktsar sahib. The therapeutic effect was observed on 21st day, 45th day and 60th

day as per the sign and symptom of pre and post treatment.

KEYWORDS: Bhringraj taila, Khalitya, Greying hair, Pitta dosha etc.

INTRODUCTION

In this present era most of the persons are living their luxury life with sedentary life style along with hectic work, stress induced factors, unhealthy dietary habits. In case of women most of them are facing these issues along with hormonal imbalance, sleep disturbances, post delivery changes in body, overuse of multiple hair products etc. All these factors lead to premature greying, hairfall, dryness of hair etc. In view of hairfall, “**Khalitya**” has been described in Ayurveda by various Acharya’s. Acharya Sushruta categorized khalitya in **Kshudra roga**.^[1] **Acharya charaka** included khalitya roga in **shiroroga**.^[2] As per **Acharya sushruta** khalitya persist due to vata and pitta predominancy by conquering the romkooa. Where as also obstruct the channel of romkooa by shleshma and shonita. In such condition an efficient treatment is needed to conquer the hairfall in a easiest and natural way without any further complication. Hence the study was done to evaluate a better treatment for khalitya, which can be adapt by patient’s in their daily life by applying hair oil (Bhringraj taila prepared in guru nanak ayurvedic college and hospital, sri muktsar sahib) in a systematic manner as well as with some dietary changes.

CASE HISTORY

Case Report - A 35 year old male patient with registration no. 22228 came to the OPD of department of Shalya tantra in Guru Nanak Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Sri Muktsar Sahib with complaint of Kasha Rukshata (dryness of hair), keshashatan (hair fall), sometime shira kandu (scalp itching).

History of Present Illness - A patient visit in OPD of Shalya tantra department in Guru Nanak Ayurvedic College, Sri Muktsar Sahib with complaints about hairfall, sometime scalp itching, greying of hair from last 7 – 8 months. The issue became more significant from last 1 month as he was in stressed condition.

History of Past Illness – There was no relevant past history of chronic or major disease.

Family History – No family history found.

PERSONAL HISTORY

1. Religion – Hindu
2. Diet – vegetarian
3. Marriage history – married

4. Micturition – normal
5. Appetite – medium
6. Sleep – disturbed
7. Bowel habit – irregular
8. Addiction – tea, alcohol
9. Saar – madhyam
10. Satmya – madhyam
11. Sahnan – madhyam
12. Vyayam – avar
13. Koshtha – krur koshthi
14. Predominant rasa – lavan and katu
15. Vihar – Diwaswapan and ratri jagran
16. Hair cosmetics – shampoo, hair serum, rebounding, hair colour
17. Type of water used – hard water

ASHTAVIDHA PAREEKSHA

1. Nadi – 72/min.
2. Mala – hard stool
3. Mutra – normal
4. Jihva – coated
5. Shabad – clear
6. Sparsha – normal
7. Drik – samyak
8. Akriti – samyak

MANAGEMENT PROTOCOL

Table no. 1: Conservative treatment.

S.NO.	FACTORS	EXTERNAL MEDICATION
1.	Name of the formulation	Bhringraja taila ^[3]
2.	Dose	5 -10 ML
3.	Route of administration	Local application
4.	Time of administration	Four times a week
5.	Duration	60 days

DIETARY HABITS**Pathya**

- Ahaar** – 1. Fruits – (fibrous fruit) narikel, draksha, amla, pomegranate, papaya, guava, lemon, orange.
2. Vegetables – cucumber, bottle gourd, sweet potato, carrot, leafy green vegetables like spinach, broccoli.
3. Others – barley, wheat, shali chawal (rice), dairy products.

Vihaar – 1. Dincharya – regular sleep schedule, avoid exposure towards heat.

2. Shiro abhyang with bhringraja taila as per suggested.
3. Practice yoga to release stress.

Apathya

Ahaar – Avoid consumption of soft drinks, alcohol, tea and caffeine, oily food, junk food.

Vihaar – Avoid harsh treatment of hair, avoid exposure to heat, avoid excessive stress, avoid altered sleep patterns, avoid hard water for hair wash.

PRECAUTIONS

1. Do not apply oil in any part of the body except head.
2. Keep oil away from the children and wash hand after massaging.
3. If any kind of rashes, burning sensation, itching arises then stop applying it.

ASSESEMENT CRITERIA

1. The assessment scale was created to evaluate the patient suffering from khalitya.

Table no. 2: Hair Fall.

S.NO.	HAIR FALL	GRADING
1.	Absent hair fall	0
2.	Mild	1
3.	Moderate	2
4.	Severe	3

Table no. 3: Dry Hair.

S.NO.	DRY HAIR	GRADING
1.	Smooth hair	0
2.	Mild hair	1
3.	Moderate hair	2
4.	Severe hair	3

Table no. 3: Itching.

S.NO.	ITCHING	GRADING
1.	Absent itching	0
2.	Mild itching	1
3.	Moderate itching	2
4.	Severe itching	3

Table No. 4: Premature Greying.

S.NO.	PREMATURE GREYING	GRADING
1.	Less than 25% hairs of scalp	0
2.	26 – 50% hairs of scalp	1
3.	51 – 75% hairs of scalp	2
4.	76 – 100% hairs of scalp	3

Table No. 5: Before and After Treatment.

S.NO.	SIGN AND SYMPTOMS	BT	AT		
			21 st day	45 th day	60 th day
1.	Hair fall	3	2	1	0
2.	Itching	2	1	1	0
3.	Premature greying	2	2	1	0
4.	Dry hair	2	2	1	1

BEFORE TREATMENT

AFTER TREATMENT**DISCUSSION**

The single case study investigated the therapeutic efficacy of bhringraj taila as bahya chikitsa for khalitya in a 35 year old patient. The result demonstrate a significant improvement in the patients symptoms, including hair fall, dry hair, itching and premature greying, over a 60 day treatment period. A reduction in hair thinning and an increase in hair volume was also observed. These findings align with traditional ayurvedic principles and are supported by existing literature on the subject.

The patient condition was diagnosed as a pitta dominant tridoshajanaya vyadhi, a concept where an imbalance of the three doshas with a primary vitiation of pitta contributes to disease. The patient aetiological factors – including sedentary lifestyle, irregular diet and stress – are consistent with factors known to aggravate pitta dosha. According to Ayurvedic texts, aggravated pitta and vata reach the hair follicles and cause hair loss, while kapha and rakta subsequently obstruct the follicles, preventing new hair growth. The patients premature greying is also a classic symptom of aggravated pitta.

The selection of **Bhringraja taila** for this case is well founded in ayurvedic pharmacology. **Bhringraja** is renowned as a keshya herb, as it is beneficial for hair health, it possess properties that are particularly effective in pacifying pitta and vata dosha, which are directly implicated in the pathogenesis of khalitya. The oils tikta nad katu tastes, combined with its ushma and laghu qualities, help to break down the follicular obstruction caused by kapha and rakta. The topical application of the oil is not only delivers the medicinal properties directly

to the scalp but also improves local blood circulation and provides nourishment to the hair roots, preventing further hair fall and build up the strength of hairs.

CONCLUSION

This case study provides compelling evidence of the therapeutic potential of **Bhringraja taila** combined with holistic Ayurvedic management for **khalitya**. The significant improvement in the patients symptom supports its use as a safe and effective alternative to modern treatments which often comes with adverse reaction.

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